

RAISING FAMILY STABILITY IN EAST AFRICA- A SOCIOECONOMIC COMPARATIVE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Family stability is a critical factor for the socioeconomic development of any society. Raising family stability is crucial and highly linked to community socioeconomic development. The foundation of all human development starts from his or her family, then the state and the region.

In East Africa, the family unit faces unique challenges due to sociocultural, economic, and political dynamics. However, the indicators show that some EAC countries, including Rwanda, have had negative family stability for various reasons, including generalized poverty and social and cultural problems. This compelled SIAS (Socioeconomic Institute for Advanced Studies) operating in Rwanda to do research, through its Africa Development Lab, on family stability in the EAC and what can be done to raise its current standards.

This research is a comparative case study of East African member states on family stability in the East African Community member states: Uganda, Tanzania, South Sudan, Somalia, Rwanda, Kenya, Democratic Republic of Congo, and Burundi. The research uses quantitative and qualitative analysis (Q2) with data and interviews to key informant techniques.

The authors examine the similarities and differences in family stability across these nations through the comparative case study and provide recommendations to improve family wellbeing and societal cohesion. The findings show that the East African community generally remain vulnerable to family stability. There is both institutional and community need to raise family stability, including mechanisms of building domestic peace, financial capability, moral and ethical values, as well as alleviating poverty in youth and parents.

Keywords: Family Stability, Household Economy, Community Development, Socioeconomic Development, East Africa.

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1.0 Introduction

Family stability is a cornerstone of socioeconomic development, forming the bedrock upon which individuals, communities, and nations are built. In East Africa, the family unit is a central institution for nurturing future generations and providing emotional and financial support to its members. However, family stability in the region faces numerous challenges driven by a complex mix of social, economic, and political factors. Rapid urbanization, cultural transitions, poverty, changing gender roles, and the effects of globalization are among the many forces that have destabilized traditional family structures.

East African countries, as part of the East African Community (EAC), share common socioeconomic challenges, yet each has unique circumstances influencing the stability of families. For instance, while Kenya and Tanzania have seen some positive trends in family stability due to improvements in education and governance, countries like Rwanda and South Sudan continue to struggle with poverty, unemployment, and sociocultural shifts. The importance of family stability in the region cannot be understated, as it directly affects the wellbeing of children, societal cohesion, and economic development. Therefore, understanding the different factors that influence family stability across East Africa is critical for designing policies and interventions aimed at enhancing the quality of life for families in the region.

This paper explores the dynamics of family stability in East Africa through a comparative case study of selected countries, including Uganda, Tanzania, South Sudan, Rwanda, and Kenya. The study examines the socioeconomic, cultural, and educational factors that influence family stability and highlights both the shared challenges and country-specific issues affecting families. Using a combination of quantitative and qualitative research methods, including interviews and data analysis, this study offers insights into the current state of family stability in East Africa and provides recommendations for improving family cohesion and resilience across the region.

2.0. Literature review

2.1 Understanding the Importance of Family Stability

Family stability is a status or condition of having a well-functioning social institution composed of parents and children who are able to make household unity, health, and progress. Family stability is understood as a good relationship either between mother and children, or children with parents.

Family stability refers to the ability of a family unit to maintain a cohesive and functional structure in the face of economic, social, and emotional challenges. It is influenced by cultural, economic, and political factors, directly impacting child development, education, mental health, and overall social wellbeing. In East Africa, many families face increasing pressures due to rapid urbanization, poverty, changing gender roles, and the influence of global culture. Borstein and Putnick (2020).

Bornstein and Putnick (2020) assert that good relationships between mothers and children help the latter develop their minds and skills quickly. Besides, they argue that family stability and mother-to-child relationships also depend on the socioeconomic condition of the household. Their study confirms that the families' wellbeing can positively impact the family relationship and enhance stability. In this study, we analyze the wellbeing capabilities of the EAC member state based on BTI Atlas data for 2024 and see what must be done to raise family stability in EAC. East African Community (2022).

Actually, basic need corresponds directly to family stability. Raising family stability means responding to people's basic needs and solving conflicts resulting from divergent family members' interests. Ndushabandi et al. (2019, p. 2) highlight that family stability issues related to conflict in Rwanda has been between spouses, children, parents, and siblings, and mostly due to difficulties in solving conflicts of interests between themselves – whether related to materials or moral aspects. It was highlighted that in less educated families, conflict sometimes turns more violent than in educated ones. Ndushabandi et al. (2019)

In the research conducted through Group Level Assessment of homeless people, Williams-Arya et al. (2021) highlight that the needed prerequisites stipulated by the responded for having family stability were: (1) job and housing stability, (2) education and skill development, (3) emotional support, and (4) improving shelter life. This highlights that material belongings and other means of production and income of the household play an important role in family stabilities.

Job enables people to earn and generate income for the family. Kids need food, school fees, medical insurance that are necessary for their happiness, and an obligation to the parent to provide for them. For the family to exist peacefully, income is necessary. Therefore, raising family stability requires raising family income and giving responsible parents the facility to earn or manage revenues for better family expenditure. Housing stability is also important when we talk about jobs. The stressful problem as mentioned by homeless families in the abovementioned research, is where to live and set that influence their living and family stability.

Education and skills development enables family stability due to the fact that educated persons are enlightened about family responsibilities and management. Even in crisis, educated persons manage their families well in overcoming difficulties or disagreements.

Emotional support is also paramount. The study shows that family stability is linked with the psychological conditions of one of the parents and children. A family member needs to be emotionally strong to manage the relationship. Some cases may be difficult to manage, but the family can be happy, healthy, and socioeconomically prosperous with a good understanding, good mood, and good attitude. A stressed mother will, of course, affect the kids and the stressed further will not implant love in the family's livelihood unless he or she is emotionally supported.

2.2 Background of Family Stability in East Africa in Relevance to Socioeconomic and Economic Development

The East African region comprises countries with diverse histories, cultural backgrounds, and developmental trajectories. However, shared socioeconomic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, and underdevelopment have affected the stability of families in the region. This paper focuses on Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, and South Sudan, examining how these factors influence family stability and what measures can be implemented to enhance family resilience. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023), Dodoo, and Frost (2016).

The condition of living affects family stability. Williams-Arya et al. (2021) suggest that a good environment in terms of beauty or mood affects family stability heavily. The shelter must be well equipped to enable the wellbeing of the family. The condition of shelter is crucial for family stability. As humans, we need to have a clean and safe environment for our own good and for the family care, Ahmed et al. (2020). However, the existing research shows a family stability problem in the East African Community Member states. Most of the indicators rank EAC member state family stability as low and below 50% for the rest of the eight countries except Kenya and Tanzania, which are in the middle. Our contribution to this research area is to compare family stability, see the challenges, and analyze how EAC member states can overcome that problem. Dodoo, and Frost (2016).

Economic stability plays a critical role in maintaining family cohesion. Families with secure livelihoods are better positioned to provide for their members, support education, and avoid stress-related conflicts. In East Africa, economic challenges such as unemployment and underemployment strain family resources, particularly in rural areas. Many households are dependent on informal labor markets, which are highly unstable.

In Kenya and Rwanda, where the middle class is expanding, economic disparities still affect family stability. While some families thrive due to entrepreneurial opportunities and education, others face economic instability due to rising living costs, especially in urban areas. Poverty in rural regions leads to migration to cities, causing family fragmentation. Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (2020), Ndushabandi et al. (2019)

Uganda's and South Sudan's economies are still largely agrarian, and rural families depend on subsistence farming. The lack of access to modern farming technologies and markets leads to food insecurity and economic vulnerability. This results in poor educational outcomes and healthcare access, which destabilizes the family structure.

In Tanzania, the economy has experienced growth due to tourism and natural resources, yet rural poverty remains widespread. Economic policies to increase employment have had mixed results, with many families still dependent on agriculture and informal work. This creates a precarious family environment, particularly in terms of income stability.

2.3 Background of Family Stability in East Africa in Relevance to Cultural and Social Norms

Cultural norms shape family roles, responsibilities, and expectations. In East Africa, patriarchy often dominates, with traditional gender roles assigning men as providers and women as caregivers. Changes in economic conditions and global cultural shifts are challenging these norms, leading to tension within family units.

Kenyan and Rwandan families are diverse, with urban families adopting more progressive values, while rural families retain traditional norms. Urbanization and globalization have led to changes in family dynamics, particularly regarding gender roles. Women's increased participation in the workforce has altered traditional power structures, sometimes leading to conflict. Dodoo, and Frost (2016).

In Uganda and South Sudan, polygamy is still practiced in some communities, contributing to complex family structures that affect stability. The extended family system plays a crucial role in child-rearing and economic support, but this structure is under strain due to economic pressures and the shift towards nuclear family models. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024).

Tanzania's family structures are influenced by tribal affiliations and Islamic practices, particularly along the coast. Family decision-making is often collective, with extended family networks providing support. However, as families move towards nuclear models, traditional support structures are weakening, affecting family stability.

2.4 Role of Education in Family Stability in East Africa

Education is a key determinant of family stability, as it impacts income generation, decision-making, and child-rearing practices. Educated families are generally more stable, as education promotes better communication, problem-solving, and conflict-resolution skills. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024)

In Kenya and Rwanda, educational attainment has improved significantly, with many families seeing education as a path to upward mobility. However, in rural areas, access to quality education remains a challenge. The disparity in educational outcomes between urban and rural families has created a divide in family stability. Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (2020).

Uganda's universal primary education policy has increased enrollment, but the quality of education remains a concern. Families with educated parents tend to be more stable and resilient, as they can navigate economic challenges more effectively. However, high dropout rates, particularly among girls, contribute to family instability. Harkness and Super (1992).

Tanzania's education system has improved, but many families still face barriers to access, particularly in rural areas. Early marriage and teenage pregnancies disrupt the educational opportunities of young girls, destabilizing family units in the long run. Tanzania Social Action Fund (2020).

3.0 Implementation of Family Stability Theories on Contemporary EAC Practices

3.1 The Planned Behavior Theory

The planned behaviour theory assumes that behaviour plays a big role in successful human action. For instance, patience, consistency, caring, parenting, and other good behaviours play a role in human action development. As the family is the best place to support human security and psychological wellbeing, building behaviour that promotes that security is crucial. Iranizadeh et al. (2021) developed a model focusing on four themes and eight subthemes to develop a friendly and flexible family environment. The former consists of behavioural intention, attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioural control, while the latter consists of self-control, patience, control of luxury-seeking, self-esteem, parenting, need satisfaction, positive attitudes toward marriage, and attainment of peace. These components need to be developed while educating families with different problems to cope with them and look for solutions to their challenges. Since “the family is the best emotional, social, and psychological shelter for its members,” teaching them and developing young couples’ behaviour may lead to future family harmony.

The concept is that for successful family stability, the teaching of good behaviour is the primary goal to prepare for family stability between members. The problem is that these teachings are no longer systematized in a way that young people or couples internalize them before they are engaged in building new families. Given the nature of violence, these time, poverty, and busy schedules in both developed and developing societies, formal teaching to young couples on family responsibilities, issues, and ways to solve them are underestimated. Iranizadeh et al. (2021)

For most difficult situations, socioeconomic resilience for youth and parents is paramount to overcoming challenges of individuals, families, and communities related to family issues that undermine stability and progress, especially in developing nations. Youth resilience is the ability to be more positive, adaptable, and actively responsive to societal problems despite the challenges, Buheji (2018, p. 147).

According to Buheji (2018, p. 148), for a healthy family relationship, people need to avoid overprotecting the children as if they are the ones who will not make mistakes. As the experience of EU education reform since 1990s, allowing a child to learn from mistakes can guarantee improvement. Moreover, families need to avoid considering youth as bullies and victims, as this label limits their capacity to develop positive character, which is necessary for family stability (Buheji, 2018, p. 148).

For Walsh, 2011 family resilience leads to stability. Family resilience is the ability of families to withstand and rebound from disruptive life challenges, strengthen, and be more resourceful (Walsh, 2011). According to her, family resilience consists of beliefs, organization, and communication.

Belief is part of family resilience that helps its members find meaning in adversity, cultivates hope, and brings in a positive attitude to foster peace and good relationships among family members. A family without belief is hardly harmonious because it is easily shaken. Family spirituality based on Islam, Christianity, or community traditions is paramount for family stability depending on how the culture or religion defines the family structure and values and the purpose of existence.

For Walsh (2021) this gives an individual member of the family a bigger purpose in life and coexistence, and it helps the family see the crisis as a transformative opportunity for growth and ability to overcome common challenges by “can-do” something for others.

Organizational part of family resilience means that family structure, mutual support, and connectedness build family stability. According to Walsh (2011), resilient families possess flexible and stable characteristics since family members are open to change, ready to face unshaken situations, and nurturing and dependable to each other. The reason for being connected is to guarantee security to each other, trust, and mutual help. The family members’ collaborative system ensures synergy and a condition sine qua non for their stability, social capital and protracted network.

Communication is part of family resilience, which brings values of openness, tolerance, and mutual encouragement. It fosters emotional support, and opinions are given freely to express need and encouragement. According to Walsh (2011), communication enhances the problem-solving mechanisms of the family. The more people know the problem concerning one or all family members, the more they will participate in solving it.

Communication builds empathy and mobilizes resources for the family's betterment and stability. With the progress of social media, most families are now connected through WhatsApp groups and Facebook, and they can do whatever it takes to solve one problem, including sending money or other forms of socioeconomic and financial contribution for one of the members in need of help within short time – smart living.

3.2 Institutional Stability Theory

Family stability depends on a given country or community's institutional set-up and institutional stability. For the success of family stability, institutional coherence matters much. Lohwasser et al. (2022) urge that when institutions are favourable, families become more stable and successful in business. Through a meta-analysis of 142 studies from 36 countries, they did research on how the institutional environment moderates the relationship between family involvement and firm performance. They compared family and nonfamily firms using property rights protection, institutional stability, and moderation of a country’s regime type. Their findings show that institutional stability is a decisive moderator of the relationship between family involvement and firm performance. Family firms outperform nonfamily firms in democracies and autocracies but not in anocracies (chaotic, where there is no good governance). In short, family firms depend heavily on institutional stability. Lohwasser et al. (2022)

As EAC members state are starting to be stable socially, politically, etc., raising family stability would be a current and next step. However, some institutions are unstable, including in the states or regions like Eastern DRC, South Sudan, Somalia, and Burundi where we see volatility in institutional stability. This obviously affects the EAC family stability mechanism. Institutions like culture, land tenure, and inheritance structure, functioning government, justice system, market structure, etc need stability to influence the family establishment of peace and wellbeing. East African Community (2022).

For instance, research in Rwanda shows that half of the family conflict is due to land ownership problems and inheritance. Government institutions, especially in the Musanze district, always struggle to solve land ownership issues for stability in conflicting family members (Rukema and Khan, 2018). In Rwanda, the law abolished the obligation of parents to give inheritance to their family members. Still parents can do, but they are no longer legally obliged to. Harkness and Super (1992).

Overall, the social protection programs established in EAC, especially in Kenya and Rwanda, have helped improve family stability. However, gaps in healthcare and employment policies continue to strain families. While in Uganda and South Sudan, social welfare programs are still limited, with most families relying on community-based support systems. The lack of government intervention in areas such as healthcare, education, and employment exacerbates family instability, particularly in rural areas. While in Tanzania has made strides in implementing family-oriented policies, especially in healthcare and education.

However, these programs are often underfunded, limiting their impact on improving family stability. More focus is needed on social protection and employment creation to ensure long-term family cohesion. African Development Bank (2021), World Bank. (2020).

3.3 Post-divorce Life and Family Stability

Yongmin et al. (2009) highlight that in whatever cases, post-divorce livelihood affects the academic performance of children. In the study they made, girls were more affected than boys in less performance after their parents divorced. This situation is exacerbated by the fact that the family's income goes down due to divorce. In mathematics and social studies, , kids were heavily affected by the divorce of their parents. In their study, three waves of panel data from 7,897 adolescents in the National Education Longitudinal Studies have been used to investigate whether a stabilized post-divorce family environment positively affects the adolescents' academic performance trajectories. Their analyses indicate that compared with peers who grow up in stable post-divorce families, children of divorced parents who experience additional family transitions other than stabilization, either due to financial decline of the household or other problems, during late adolescence, make less progress in their math and social studies performance.

Moreover, Yongmin et al. (2009), highlight that daughters in unstable post-divorce families appear to make less academic progress over time than sons. Their study illustrates the need to incorporate both post-divorce family transitions and repeatedly measured child outcomes in the investigation of divorce effects once there is a need to raise family stability and counteract the negative effect of divorce on families. Given that family divorces are increasing in EAC member states, including Rwanda and Kenya, raising family stability requires counteracting divorces and their effects and fostering stabilization of divorced families for the sake of children's livelihood, including educational performance.

3.4 Wellbeing and Family Stability

Bornstein and Putnick (2020). They assert that a good relationship between mothers and children help the latter develop fast both in their minds and skills. Besides, Bornstein and Putnick (2020) assert that family stability and mother-to-child relationships also depend on the socioeconomic condition of the household. Their study confirms that the families' wellbeing can positively impact the family relationships and enhance stability.

This confirms that basic need corresponds directly to family stability. Raising family stability also means responding to people's basic needs, which is still problematic for most families in the EAC member states. In the research conducted through Group Level Assessment of homeless people, Williams-Arya et al. (2021) highlight that the needed prerequisites stipulated by the respondents for having family stability were: (1) job and housing stability, (2) education and skill development, (3) emotional support, and (4) improving shelter life. Buheji and Muhorakeye (2023)

The job enables people to earn and generate income for the family. Kids need food, school fees, medical insurance, etc., that are necessary for their happiness – same as parents. For the family to exist peacefully, income is a necessity. Therefore, raising family stability requires raising family income and giving responsible parents the facility to earn or manage revenues for better family expenditure. Housing stabilise also important when a stressful problems, as mentioned by homeless families, is where to live and set that influence their living and family stability.

Education and skills development enables family stability since educated persons are Enlightened about family responsibilities and management. Even in crisis, educated persons manage their families well in overcoming difficulties or disagreements.

Emotional support is also paramount. The study shows that family stability is linked with the psychological conditions of one of the parents and children. A family member needs to be emotionally strong to manage the relationship. Some cases may be challenging to manage, but the family can be happy with good understanding, good mood, and attitude. A stressed mother will, of course, affect the kids, and the stressed further will not implant love in the family's livelihood unless he or she is emotionally supported.

4.0 Methodology

This study adopts a comparative case study approach, utilizing qualitative and quantitative data from Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, South Sudan, and Rwanda. Data collection involves literature reviews, government reports, and family welfare studies. Interviews and focus groups were conducted with families, social workers, and policymakers across the three countries to gather insights on how families cope with challenges.

In this research, the authors used 'working with data' techniques, which were quantitative methods, and 'key informant interview', which were qualitative methods. We compared different EAC member state data from BTI Atlas Transformational Family Stability Index for quantitative data. Transformation data highlight the level at which societies get a better standard of living. They are synchronically analyzed based on the year 2024. We did tabulation and interpretation.

The key informant has been selected from the people who faced domestic violence, issues with their parents, or who had a conflict with siblings or spouses, especially in Rwanda, Kenya, and South Sudan. We had at least ten key informants to support our empirical data.

The study is grounded in the social-ecological model, highlighting the interaction between individuals and their environment as key to understanding family stability. This model allows for an analysis of how different levels—individual, interpersonal, community, and policy—affect the family unit.

The research structure is divided into two parts in terms of interpretation. The first is quantitative, while the second is qualitative, with the aim to support each other.

4.0. FINDINGS

4.1 Quantitative analysis on comparative transformational Index of family stability in EAC member state and how to raise family stability in Each one

Family Stability Index	Uganda /10	Tanzania /10	South Sudan /10	Somalia /10	Rwanda /10	Kenya /10	Democ. Republic of Congo /10	Burundi /10
General situation/ status of the country	4.8	5.1	2.2	1.7	4.5	5.8	3.3	3.4
Socioeconomic level	2	6	1	1	2	3	1	1
Resource efficiency	4	4.3	1.7	1.3	6.3	3.7	2	2.7
Rule of law	4.3	4.3	2.3	1	3.3	6	2.8	2.5
Stateness	7.3	7.5	4.5	2	8.3	6	5.5	6.5
Private property	6.5	7	3	2.5	6	7	3.5	4
Welfare regime	4.5	5	2.5	1	5.5	5.5	1	4
Economic performance	6	6	1	2	5	7	6	3
Steering capability	3.3	6	1.3	2.7	5.7	6	2.7	4.3
Sociopolitical integration	4.7	5	2	2.7	2.7	5.8	4.3	4
Consensus building	4.8	6	2.2	2.4	3.8	5	2.8	2.6

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Family Stability Index	Uganda /10	Tanzania /10	South Sudan /10	Somalia /10	Rwanda /10	Kenya /10	Democ. Republic of Congo /10	Burundi /10
General Observations	There are lot of needed improvements in terms of socioeconomic performance in Uganda order to foster family stability. The rule of law and welfare status need improvements too.	Tanzania is performing well in terms of family stability index but need more appropriate approaches on rule of law and resource efficiency.	Economic performance is too low and this can affect heavily family stability	Socioeconomic level and rule of law are too low to make family stability environment	Some cases of violent intra-family conflict. And family conflict over land	2/3 of the families have poor nutrition, diseases and women and marginalized people are more affected.	Socioeconomic level, welfare of the household are too low to foster stability within families	Domestic poverty level is high. Land tenure issues exist mixed post conflict repatriation management

Source: numbers are from the BTI Atlas 2024, interpreted and analyzed by authors.

The data shows that only Kenya and Tanzania have positive family stability indexes thanks to general society governance and socioeconomic data. Others are on the negative side, However, though Tanzania and Kenya are at a good pace, they are also low if we compare them with other regions or if we look at a single country's livelihood situation. For instance, the majority of Kenyans are living in poverty at the household level and have problems with nutrition and healthy life.

4.2. Qualitative Analysis of 'Family Stability' Basing on Group Discussion

The findings show that people from East Africa still have challenges regarding family stability, including a healthy, caring, and responsible family. Some mentioned that their partners have violently harassed them. While talking to Anatole¹ he said:

“I was standing, putting my arms in my back, then my wife came with a machete and cut me”. We have kids with her now I abandoned my house and only support them. I left the house and land for her and my children and married another one we live with. She mostly asks me for money and I give her, five, ... thousand Rwanda money, for instance, in the case of last evening” as a carpenter. The first wife had a concubine who was a motorcyclist taxman they had a child and I recognised her as my child, not biologically, but I took care of the baby together with my own blood children. Now I live with my other wife, who I married later, and we have two kids. I regret I would have married her earlier, we love each other, the former I did not manage to live with her before marriage and people just called me while I was in the city that I had to come with nice wedding cloths, and make a civil marriage ceremony. I did not love her, but we had children together before civil marriage”.

Rwanda adopted a monogamy policy during the colonial period, and until now, the law obliges families who live together without civil marriage to do so publically and mostly by force. This sometimes creates women's power to claim properties and divide equally with men even though she might have come into the husband's family without anything. The new gender laws enable some women and men to be free riders on properties they did not work for.

In that framework, the Rwandan government did not enforce polygamy as in the case of some EAC countries, for instance, Kenya, but had newly established laws that balance property sharing and put some equity between husband and wife. This law stipulates that a woman who is not legally married has the right to some of her husband's properties once they have been together for some years, the same as her husband. The law provides some percentage whether they are officially married or not.

There is an increase in divorce, though mostly close to 40% in Kigali (Source...). During the interview, some young women told us that they had been abandoned by men when they had been together for a few months and lived with them with pregnancy.

“My husband was studying in IPRC South and abandoned me when I was pregnant. Now I have a baby, and I struggle myself to take care of him alone. I had to start a menial job to survive, including working the people's farm for 2000 Frw a day.

¹ The name which represent the interviewed man in Huye district in Rwanda

This kept me living with my child. He no longer calls me, and even when I talk to his mother, she mentions that she does not care about that and that it was between us”.

Some irresponsibility of one of the parents puts family stability at risk. Generally, women suffer from men who abandon them carelessly while they are in the critical time of life as they are pregnant and unable to work for menial jobs. In Rwanda, the government established a mechanism to support women who gave birth while they were still living with their families, especially those from low-income families of category one or two of the *Ubudehe* classification. This is to empower women and increase their survival capacity.

In the case of other South Sudan, for instance, the people I interviewed informed me that they are burdened mainly by the culture stipulating that once you are merry in one family, that family expects the bridegroom to start responsible for caring for the family in law. Although this is a good culture for South Sudanese and many African societies, it may trigger the son-in-law to be overburdened since the current costs are heavier than traditional given the demands rising from his new family.

“I have two wives, the first one is living in Germany and the second in South Sudan. I managed to complete the school fees of my brothers in law now. It is our cultural obligation to take care of them. I feel more released and happy”. South-Sudanese.

They are also girls who testify that once they get married, the husband will be responsible for caring for most of her family members, especially siblings. This culture is good if we consider extended family stability, but given the trends in globalization and the cost of living, it is hard. This happens to both young and older people, depending on vulnerability. However, there are still gaps in establishing healthy, wealthy, and responsible families given exogenous factors in East Africa, including generalized poverty, illiteracy, and distortion of traditional family values.

5.0 Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Learning from the Findings of the Comparative Study

This comparative case study reveals that family stability in East Africa is influenced by a complex interplay of socioeconomic, economic, cultural, and Education-related factors. While some challenges are shared across the region, such as poverty and unemployment, the ways in which these issues manifest differ from country to country. In Kenya, urbanization and gender roles present unique challenges, while in Uganda, polygamy and rural poverty are critical factors. In the mean while, Tanzania faces a blend of traditional and modern pressures that impact family structures.

The findings show that the East Africa region has a severe problem related to family stability, and both qualitative and quantitative support this argument. For instance, in terms of stable marriage, divorce is increasing. In terms of stability for new young couples, we see irresponsibility between husband and wife, which heavily affects their children’s livelihood. The finding further shows that there is a lack of preparedness for family building and a low level of teaching on how to take the marriage seriously, how to be patient, what to do when domestic conflict arises, and the empathy and responsibility of each family member.

There is a need to establish socioeconomic institutions that foster family preparedness, provide teaching and values to young couples, and even remind the elderly. Civic and community or religious institutions need to embed this kind of teaching. Researchers and skilled people would discover those specific teachings and how they can be thoughtfully implemented.

The quantitative data shows that family stability also goes hand in hand with economic levels. The data shows that the more empowered family members, especially the parents, the more stable provisions there are. Countries with low GDP levels, including South Sudan, and DRC, have a lot of family stability problems, though generally, the entire East Africa region ranks low. There is a need to raise family income for parents to be able to pay the cost of raising families, but the general economy and societal values also need to be strengthened to build family stability.

5.2 Proposed Framework for Enhancing Family Stability in EAC

Based on the outcome of this study, certain family stability variables can be integrated into a multidimensional framework that allows for an in-depth understanding of the factors influencing family stability in East African countries (EAC). By analyzing these variables across different EAC countries and contexts, this study can offer a comprehensive view of the region's challenges and opportunities for enhancing family wellbeing.

The proposed framework in Figure (1) represents the type of leakages we need to close to enhance family stability in EAC. Thus, the dependent variable in this framework is family stability (as measured by family cohesion, conflict levels, and overall wellbeing). At the same time, the independent variables would be the economic status, cultural norms, education levels, health and wellbeing, institutional support, and environmental factors.

Figure (1) Illustration of Framework for Enhancing Family Stability in EAC

5.3 Implications of the Study

To raise family stability in East Africa, a multi-pronged approach is necessary. Governments should prioritize social protection programs that support vulnerable families, particularly in rural areas. Policies should also focus on improving access to education and healthcare, which are key to building resilient families. Culturally sensitive interventions that respect traditional norms while promoting gender equality and modern family dynamics are essential for long-term stability.

Future research should delve deeper into the role of global influences, mainly social media and migration, in shaping family stability in East Africa. Understanding these dynamics will be crucial in designing policies and programs that ensure the wellbeing of families in the region.

We recommend more comparative research on family stability among the sub-region, or groups of people, and family stability mechanisms between different sociocultural institutions, including Muslims, Christians, and traditional religions in East Africa. There is also a research gap on the effectiveness of public policies and community engagements that aim at raising family stability in EAC, for instance, in terms of knowing different EAC member states' different strategies, how effective and efficient there are, and what one country can learn from others within or outside the community.

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